

GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT RATES OF CALVES OF DIFFERENT BREEDS.

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Annotation: The database on the growth of young cattle is based on the example of black-and-white and Holsteinized black-and-white calves bred for dairy purposes.

Keywords. Semen, growth, development, live weight, absolute gain, relative gain, pedigree.

Introduction. An integral part of the priority agricultural sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, animal husbandry is an important and diversified sector of the national economy. Its significance is determined by the fact that it provides the population with valuable food products, and light industry with the necessary raw materials. Today, about 10 different breeds of cattle are bred in all types of farms in the country. Of these, the black desert, red desert and Bushuev breeds are dairy, the Swiss and cement breeds are mixed breeds, and the Santa Gertrude, Kazakh white-headed and Aberdeen Angus breeds are meat breeds. It is important to ensure targeted growth and development of young cattle. Feeding schemes and diets adopted on farms must be such as to ensure the growth and development of calves in accordance with the breeding plan and feeding norms. At the same time, it is necessary to save on expensive nutrients such as milk and concentrates. The only food for calves within 10-15 days after birth is milk, the feeding of which depends on the planned daily weight gain of the cow.

Materials and methods. For the experiment, we conducted a study to study the growth, development, and some biological features of calves belonging to the black-and-white and Holstein-black breeds in the conditions of the farms "Besh bola" and "Sevar" Pastdargom district of Samarkand region. We conducted a

practical production experiment. For the experiment, calves of similar origin, sex, and age were included in a group of 10 heads based on similarity. The feeding and care conditions of the experimental group were the same.

Results obtained and their analysis. It is known that the feeding of animals, including cattle, is one of the factors influencing their growth and development. During the experiment, we intensively fed the animals with a ration of home-grown fodder. In our experiment, the study of the growth rate of calves is one of the main indicators, because the growth of a young organism depends primarily on the level of nutrition.

One of the indicators of the proper development of young cattle is the change in their live weight. With this in mind, we determined the live weights of the animals in the experimental group by months and presented them in Table 1 below.

From the data in this table, it can be seen that before the experiment, the average live weight of black-and-white calves on the Besh bola Farm was 33.5 kg, while that of Holstein black-and-white was 38.1 kg. The average live weight of black-and-white calves on the Sevar farm was 34.2 kg, and the average weight of black-and-white calves was 37.6 kg. For 30 days, the average live weight of black-and-white calves on a Besh bola farm was 54.3 kg, an increase of 20.8 kg on average over a month. The average daily weight gain of calves was 695 g, compared to the absolute live weight gain of calves compared to the initial live weight, which is 62.1%.

The live weight of black-and-white calves on the Sevar farm after 30 days was 52.2 kg, ie the absolute increase was 18.0 kg, and the average daily growth of calves was 600 g, the live weight of Holsteinized black-and-white calves after 30 days was 58.4 kg, and the average daily growth of calves was 695 g.

These data show that the absolute growth of calves after 30 days of the experiment is 2.8 kg higher than that of black-and-white calves at Besh Bola farm and black-and-white calves at Sevar farm. which was 95 g higher than the average daily growth of calves.

Table 1

Calf growth rate

Age of calves	BESH BOLA a farm specializing in cattle breeding				SEVAR a farm specializing in cattle breeding			
	I-group Black and white		II-group Holsteized black-and-white		III-group Black and white		IV-group Holsteized black-and-white	
At birth	Live weight, kg	-	38,1	-	34,2	-	37,5	-
1 st month	Absolute growth, kg	20,8	62,1	24,0	52,2	18,0	58,4	20,8
	Average daily growth, g	695	800	800	600	600	695	695
2 nd month	Relative growth, %	62,1	63,0	63,0	52,6	52,6	53,7	53,7
	Absolute growth, kg	20,1	85,3	23,2	70,0	17,8	78,5	20,1
3 rd month	Average daily growth, g	670	775	775	595	595	670	670
	Relative growth, %	27,4	28,6	28,6	26,3	26,3	26,5	26,5
90 days	Live weight, kg	95,5	109,7	71,6	88,4	54,2	99,5	61,9
	Average daily growth, g	690,0	796,6	796,6	603,3	603,3	688,3	688,3
	Relative growth, %	185,07	188,0	188,0	158,5	158,5	164,6	164,6

After 60 days of calves, the average live weight of black-and-white calves on the Besh bola Farm reached 74.4 kg, an increase of 20.1 kg over 30 days, with the average daily calf weight. The average live weight of Holsteinized black-and-white calves was 85.3 kg, an increase of 20.1 kg over 30 days, and the average daily growth of calves was 670 g. Idi. This figure is 70.0 kg in black-and-white calves of Sevar farm, the absolute increase in live weight of calves for 30 days was 17.8 kg, with an average daily gain of 595 g. is coming. Holsteinized black-and-white calves weighed 78.5 kg, with an absolute live weight gain of 20.1 kg over 30 days, compared to an average daily gain of 670 g.

The live weight of calves at the end of the experiment was as follows: 95.5 kg in the black-and-white group of five children on the farm, 109.7 kg in the black-and-white group, 88.4 kg in the black-and-white calves on the Sevar farm. 99.5 kg in black and white. Absolute growth of calves for 90 days: 62.0 kg in the black-and-white group of five children on the farm, 71.6 kg in the black-and-white group on the farm, 54.2 kg in the black-and-white calves on the Sevar farm, we can see that it was 61.9 kg in the hollowed-out black.

Conclusion

An analysis of the results showed that our studies showed that calves of different breeds had similar numbers, which indicates that the calves were at a good level. However, these calves can be used in the future to create high-yielding dairy herds.

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